

Assessing functionality and usability of a virtual tour for nature engagement: brief report

Anna Conniff, Phoebe Somervail and Katherine N Irvine, James Hutton Institute, June 2024

Introduction

Virtual tours are increasingly used as a means of enabling people to explore a location without having to be there physically. Utilising 360° photographs, virtual tours are used to advertise real estate, promote holiday destinations, and share historical reconstructions of ancient places. While they have also been used to showcase different outdoor places such as woodlands, highlighting viewpoints and particular points of interest, tours of these types of areas do not typically enable people to follow a route from start to finish.

We are seeking to understand how different visual methods can help facilitate understanding and development of nature engagement capabilities in members of the public. For this work, we have developed a virtual tour of an outdoor walking path. Here, we outline the construction of the tour, its evaluation through survey and focus group, and its future potential applications.

Our research goals were to understand: (i) whether a 'walkable' virtual tour of a path is easily usable by members of the public on different types of devices; (ii) what type of additional content is seen as valuable; (iii) whether the tour enables viewers to feel like they know what the location would be like in situ; and (iv) the types of people/groups that might benefit from such tours.

Virtual Nature Tour: Cashel Forest Oak Path

Cashel Forest is on the east side of Loch Lomond within Loch Lomond and The Trossachs National Park (LLTNP). LLTNP are keen to promote Cashel Forest as it is currently an undervisited resource that is located only a few miles north of the well-known, highly visited Balmaha. The site offers similar views to the popular Conic Hill, as well as a range of walks of different lengths and for differing abilities. We created a virtual tour of one of these walks, the Oak Path (Figure 1), using 3DVista software.

Figure 1. Opening position of the first 360° photograph in the virtual tour of the Cashel Forest Oak path, with the visitor centre on the left and showing the blue 'i' hotspots indicating that further information is available.

Following the circular Oak Path in a clockwise direction from start to finish, the tour is comprised of 38 360° photographs and one timelapse video. Its design incorporates the following:

- A front page providing both instructions on how to navigate the tour and an overview of the Oak Path itself, detailing practical accessibility information such as the number and types of benches and steepness of the incline at one particular point.
- An aerial map view in the top right-hand corner of the screen which indicates current location on the path, with 7 clickable hotspots which link directly to the additional content presented on the route of the tour (photographic slideshows of flora, insect life, and seasonal differences; videos of badgers; and audio recordings of birdsong and burns).
- Links to additional information sources such as the Scottish Outdoor Access Code, LLTNP website, and the Cashel Forest website and Facebook page. These links are available from the 360° photograph of the inside of the visitor centre.
- Information on Cashel Forest's location, parking charges, and visitor centre opening times.

The tour can be viewed at <https://virtualtours.hutton.ac.uk/cashelforestoakpath/>. While best viewed on a larger screen, the tour can be viewed on any computer, tablet, or mobile device.

Evaluation approach

We piloted our virtual tour using a think-aloud method with participants, which enabled us to understand what parts of the tour needed to be improved to enhance ease of use. Following the pilot stage, we promoted the tour with an accompanying survey via Twitter/X and through friends and family networks. Following analyses of the survey results, we conducted an online focus group with five members of the public to further explore topics of relevance.

Key findings from survey and focus group

After data cleaning, there were 50 genuine respondents to our survey¹. Of these, 54% (n=27) were female, and 72% (n=36) were between the ages of 25 and 54. Four respondents (8%) indicated that they had a disability that impacts their use of the outdoors.

Using the virtual tour

Ninety percent (n=45) of respondents reported that the instructions on how to navigate the virtual tour were clear or very clear. Eighty-four percent (n=42) found it easy or very easy to navigate through the tour (2 participants found it difficult or very difficult). Respondents reported using a variety of methods to navigate the tour, depending on the device they were using. 34% (n=17) used a phone or tablet, while the remainder used a combination of mouse or onscreen arrows on desktop or laptop computer. Taken together, these findings give us confidence that the tour is easy to use, across a variety of devices.

We wanted to know whether the aerial map was a helpful feature. Of the respondents who reported using the aerial map (84%, n=42), the main reasons included: (i) to figure out where they were on the Oak Path (ii) to check what direction they were facing and, (iii) to jump between hotspots on the map.

Additional content features

Figure 2 details survey feedback on the content features. The time-lapse video was reported as least helpful. Reasons provided were that it was felt to be too fast, and to not add value to the tour overall. Respondents found the slideshows and wildlife videos helpful. Approximately 40% (n=20) reported that they did not use the links to external websites 'housed' in the visitor centre.

Focus group participants similarly had not used the external links. Discussion identified that this was because it was not clear that the visitor centre was a part of the tour to be explored. If participants did not choose to move around the first 360° photograph, they would miss the arrow directing them inside

¹ Promotion via Twitter/X generated a large number of invalid responses from bots. This issue, and its implication for future surveys promoted via social media, is discussed in our full report.

the visitor centre (see Figure 1 for initial viewpoint of this photograph). This is a functionality issue that we will address in future versions of the tour.

Figure 2. Survey responses on the helpfulness of the additional content features.

Effectiveness of the virtual tour in communicating what a location is like

Eighty-eight percent (n=44) of survey respondents said they were more likely to visit Cashel Forest having engaged with the tour. When asked if the virtual tour provided enough information to understand what it would be like to visit the path in real life, 90% (n=45) of people said yes. 90% (n=45) also felt they could confidently visit Cashel Forest in person from the information provided in the tour. Those who did not feel they could confidently visit wanted more information on facilities, public transport, and a map of the location of the forest.

Ideas for enriching the virtual tour content

We asked participants for their ideas about improving the tour. Suggestions included:

- More site-specific information: the history of the woods; oaks and oak ecology; names and information about the insects and plants featured in the slideshows.
- Information about different weather (and midge!) conditions at Cashel Forest throughout the year, and what to wear.
- Precise locations of the benches and picnic bench.
- More footage from off the path, for example, showing views.
- More wildlife videos.
- Videos from different viewpoints e.g. looking over the footbridge at the burn below, to increase the realism of the experience.
- More audio clips e.g. the woods in windy conditions, crunchy leaves underfoot.
- Links to information about the birds in the woods and what they sound like e.g. Wildlife Trust/RSPB websites.

Making the tour a more immersive experience through the addition of more audio and more 'as if I was there' details (such as looking over the side of the bridge) was expanded upon by one focus group participant. This individual explained how she explored the tour while playing a forest ambience soundtrack, which helped her feel like she was there. She also indicated that she had really wanted to experience the tour using a VR headset. This is something that can be easily catered for in 3DVista, and we will enable this feature in future versions of the tour.

Who might benefit from tours like these?

We asked both survey and focus group participants for their opinions on who might benefit from viewing such a virtual tour before visiting the location in real life. Responses included:

- Families with buggies or small children to understand what the facilities and path are like.
- Dog walkers to understand what the route is like.
- Elderly people or people with reduced mobility to see what the terrain and resting points are like.
- People with physical disabilities to understand whether it would be possible for them to manage the path on their own, or with assistance from friends/family.
- People with anxiety, neurodivergence/autistic spectrum disorder, for whom visiting new places can be stressful.
- Preparing school classes ahead of a school visit or residential trip.
- Leaders of groups such as brownies/scouts/school classes sourcing locations for trips; forest school leaders.

One focus group participant with disabilities that keep her effectively housebound commented that the information provided on the terrain and incline would help her know whether this was somewhere that she could ask her friends to take her with her wheelchair. Another participant, a forest school leader, commented that this type of resource would be invaluable in terms of planning where to hold classes.

Conclusions and next steps

Findings suggest that our virtual tour is straightforward and easy to use, across multiple devices for viewing. The tour provided people with confidence that they would know what to expect if they visited Cashel Forest's Oak Path in person.

We will amend the Oak Path virtual tour to address identified issues, specifically the visibility of the visitor centre. We will also enable the tour to be viewable using a mobile phone with a VR headset. We may expand the scope of the tour using additional 360° photographs taken from other paths at the Cashel Forest site to provide snapshots of what these other paths are like (without generating full step-by-step tours of these paths).

We will apply what we have learned about virtual tour construction and type of useful content for supporting development of nature engagement capabilities as we move forward with the next stage of this project. This next phase will investigate whether virtual tours can be a useful tool to encourage nature engagement among less confident and infrequent visitors to outdoor places. We will also investigate whether virtual tours can help foster and develop awareness of and skills for responsible nature engagement when in the natural environment.

Acknowledgement: This work is part of a Scottish Government RESAS-funded Strategic Research Programme project titled 'Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing' (JHI-C6-1). It corresponds to Deliverable D9 submitted as part of work package titled 'Nature engagement capabilities' (WP3).

Suggested citation: Conniff, A., Somervail, P. & Irvine, K.N. (2024). Assessing functionality and usability of a virtual tour for nature engagement: brief report. Deliverable D9 for Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1), The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen, Scotland.

For further details on this research, please see Conniff, A., Somervail, P. & Irvine, K.N. (2024) Virtual Tours of Nature: Assessing functionality and usability for fostering nature engagement. Deliverable D9 for Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1), The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen, Scotland.

Contact: For further information contact Anna Conniff (anna.conniff@hutton.ac.uk), Phoebe Somervail (phoebe.somervail@hutton.ac.uk), or Katherine Irvine (kate.irvine@hutton.ac.uk), Social, Economic and Geographical Sciences Department, The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen, AB15 8QH, Scotland, UK.